

A Comparative Study of TCP Congestion Control Protocols with NS3

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Abstract

Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) is of paramount importance in smooth data transmission over different network scenarios, besides, the congestion control mechanisms are central to strengthening the network's performance and stability. Over the years, several TCP variants—such as TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP VenO, and TCP Yeah—are the ones that have been invented to tackle the respective difficulties of handling network congestion. This research describes a well-thought and logical argument analysis of the above protocols through the implementation of ns-3 simulation environment for each protocol's performance tests through the network. The study mainly looks at major performance indicators, for example, Congestion Window dynamics, Packet Loss Rates, and Throughput. It exposes the different strengths and weaknesses of each TCP version. In the current version of ns-3, the analysis is very well validated, which in turn, broadens the comprehension and networking of TCP optimization. The differences among the individual protocols in their response styles to reduction and alleviation of traffic congestion, which can be noticed in the results that indicate the fundamental balancing in traffic control. In the latter part, this study not alone provides basic theory but also gives a practical guide to the protocol selection which helps in better decision-making for optimized TCP performance in diverse network environments.

Index Terms

TCP Congestion Control, NS3 Simulation, TCP Protocols, Network Performance, TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP VenO, TCP Yeah, Congestion Window, Packet Loss, Throughput, Network Optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) is one of the key protocols in the Internet Protocol Suite, which is tasked with the transmission of data from one host to another in an unstable network. Over the years, TCP has evolved into one of the most commonly used transport layer protocols, due to its capability of easily connecting various client applications like, say, browsers and streaming tools, hence its non-disruptive role in establishing networks of this kind worldwide. Since networks are changing all the time, effective congestion control ensures the achievement of the delays and opportunities of users using their resources simultaneously [1][2].

TCP's congestion control mechanisms are intended to control congestion, i.e., a situation where network demand continues to increase over the available resources by dynamically adjusting data rate. The number of routing algorithms of TCP to overcome network congestion problems have been TCP using innovative methods and strategies. This discussion highlights the necessity of changing according to the Environment of the network and application requirements. The TCP versions which are important in this field are TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP VenO, and TCP Yeah each employing different techniques to manage congestion and optimize performance.[3][4][5].

The paper revolves around the detailed study of the comparison of the TCP congestion control mechanisms on the NS3 simulation framework. With the help of simulations done under different sourcing processes, the paper evaluates every protocol of the meter by its core characteristics such as Congestion Window size, Packet Loss rates, and throughput. NS3 is a powerful simulation environment that allows testing and validation of network protocols, thus, aiding in the gain of in-depth insights into the working of the said protocols under realistic conditions [6][7].

The research aims to discover the strengths and weaknesses of each TCP variant, and thus the possibilities of higher network performance will be evident. The results promise to provide vital lessons to boost network architecture and protocol on the basis of which it will confer rational decision making both in the research and practical applications side. Through the study of TCP's congestion control mechanisms, this work affects debates around network optimization and the construction of more robust protocols of communication. [8][9][10][11][12].

II. PREVIOUS WORK DONE

TCP congestion control has undergone the development of new methods through research. The paper entitled "A Self-Tuning Congestion Tracking Control for TCP/AQM Network for Single and Multiple Bottleneck Topology" introduces the SRQ-PI controller, which automatically changes the packet drop probability of the network depending on how traffic is,

thus queue management becomes effective with low overshoot and fast settling time [1]. The paper "Comparative Analysis of Compound TCP with Various End-to-End Congestion Control Mechanisms" will give a study result using the NS2 simulator that demonstrates TCP CUBIC provides the winning edge in terms of throughput for networks with high-bandwidth, whereas TCP Vegas helps to avoid packet loss which is a capability of packets that can lose data [2]. The "Consensus Congestion Control for Ad Hoc Networks: Time-Delay and Saturation" introduces a new design model that adopts the graph theory framework of TCP and AQM for time-delay and input saturation issues with the positive simulation results [3]. "Enhancing TCP via Hysteresis Switching" features the technique, that brings the data hysteresis mechanism to tackle the issue of irreparable losses, thus relieving the TCP in data centers through increased throughput [4]. The PLATO technology applied in TCP, dubbed "Packet Labelling to Alleviate Time-Out," makes use of deep Q-learning for optimal congestion window tuning, thus demonstrating that, while throughput is improved, RTT is higher than with existing methods [5]. Automatically combining the Slow-Start algorithm's learning of congestion control parameters with more aggressive mechanisms to effectively reduce the number of retransmissions is the core mechanism of the TCCC protocol's Transmissions Efficiency [6]. In the paper titled "Fairness Enhancement of TCP Congestion Control Using Reinforcement Learning," an algorithm based on DQN (Deep Q-Network) that ensures both the high throughput and the fair bandwidth allocation are achieved under certain scenarios [7]. Namely, The "Comparative Analysis of TCP Congestion Control Methods" denotes that TCP Vegas as the one stands out being the most efficient, gaining the ability of early congestion detection which finally results in reduced latency and lower drop rate [8]. The work of "TCP Congestion Analysis of Wired and Wireless Links Using NS3" covering the skill-based techniques for learning apart from showcases the superseded version of TCB-DQN titled TCP-DQN [9]. Tcp Incast Incidents through Packet Size Adjustment" suggests Packet Slicing as the troupe to get around TCP Incast in data centers which wind up in greater goodput [10]. "Flow-Aware Adaptive Pacing to Mitigate TCP Incast" is a pacing scheme that not only controls TCP Incast but also substantially improves network performance presenting by means of regulating the transmission of packets [11]. Finally, "REN: Receiver-Driven Congestion Control Using Explicit Notification for Data Center" is a method that assigns the responsibility of congestion notification to the receiver which, in turn, improves the link utilization and reduces flow completion time through the use of ECN bits [12].

A. Summary of Related work

Recent research in TCP congestion control has introduced methods involving intelligent algorithm adjustments to handle congestion effectively. The SRQ-PI controller dynamically adjusts packet drop probabilities based on real-time congestion data, optimizing queue management with reduced overshoot and faster response times [1]. Studies also indicate TCP CUBIC's suitability for high congestion and TCP Vegas's effectiveness in low-data-loss scenarios [2]. A TCP/AQM model using graph theory addresses time-delay and input saturation issues, with positive simulation results [3]. Hysteresis switching is proposed to reduce non-recoverable losses in data centers [4], while TCP PLATO applies deep reinforcement learning to dynamically adjust the congestion window, enhancing throughput despite an increased round-trip time [5]. TCCC's combined slow-start and aggressive congestion avoidance strategies reduce retransmissions in mixed-flow networks [6]. A DQN-based method improves throughput and bandwidth fairness [7], and TCP Vegas has proven efficient in capturing early congestion signals, reducing latency and packet loss [8]. TCP-DQN, a machine learning-based approach, is effective in managing congestion across wired and wireless networks [9]. Techniques like packet slicing and adaptive pacing help mitigate TCP incast issues, improving reliability in data centers [10, 11]. Finally, REN uses explicit notification to optimize data transfer completion times and link efficiency in data centers with ECN bits [12].

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The existing studies show a narrow exploration of new TCP versions' behavior in different network conditions; thus, a broader investigation is necessary. Although the analysis reveals many TCP congestion control mechanisms have still been unexplored in the case of the variations of the network conditions. Hence, they are responsible for the remaining gaps in understanding. A step-by-step comparative analysis through the simulation of NS3 is needed to be carried between Compound TCP among the different variants of TCP.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The study involves creating a detailed network topology in the ns-3 simulator to allow the examination of Compound TCP vis-a-vis some multidimensional other TCP differentials, like TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP VenO, and TCP Yeah . By the time ns-3 version 3.40 is ready for use with the whole package of required dependencies it corresponds to, simulation scripts are created to model real networks by describing nodes, links, as well as the settings that we can change like queue length link bandwidths, or delay. Congestion control methods such as slow start, congestion avoidance, and fast recovery which are part of the particular characteristics of each TCP variant, are implemented with exactitude in every instance of the TCP method thus making correct simulation.

The TCP variant implementation process flowchart is illustrated in Figure 1. Apart from the measurement of the network throughput, delay, and loss, the study can also fine-tune the parameters in the hardware across multiple test scenarios to obtain

Fig. 1: Flowchart of TCP Variant Implementation

the data that represent the real situations. Simulation outputs are being received, which are then analyzed for throughput, end-to-end delay, and packet loss, along with visualizations for performance comparison. Results are compiled in a comprehensive report that highlights the specific and pronounced advantages of each variant, especially Compound TCP. Finally, the thus obtained results are referenced by theoretical and practical results of other studies in order for them to be more credible and real-life.

The methodology used in this paper was one of several stages that are crucial in order to track the changes in the congestion window. The simulation uses a very simple topology with just two nodes over a point-to-point link connected, therefore allowing the manipulation of the TCP behavior and setting. At the beginning, two nodes can be inserted through the `NodeContainer` class, which is an essential class in networks with multiple nodes. The `PointToPointHelper` is used to set up the connection to the other node with a 5 Mbps data rate and 2 ms delay. For realistic conditions to be met, slightly deviated error channel models should be assumed. Thus, the `RateErrorModel` is applied to the receiving device, to slightly deviate the error rate, making it 0.00001.

The simulation has a wide range of protocol selection with TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP VenO, and TCP Yeah all can serve as the congestion control algorithm. Configuration parameters like the initial congestion window set at 1 packet and implementation of the respective fast recovery algorithms are implemented for those specific protocols to evaluate their effect on the TCP performance in NS-3. The `InternetStackHelper` is used to configure the TCP/IP stack on both nodes, allowing for protocols to be selected to establish communication over the network.

Next, an `Ipv4AddressHelper` assigns IP addresses in the range of 10.1.1.0/30 to the nodes, facilitating their identification during the simulation. A TCP packet sink is deployed on node 1, listening on port 8080. This sink application, created using the `PacketSinkHelper`, starts at 0 seconds and stops at 20 seconds, allowing it to capture all incoming data from node 0. On node 0, a custom application, referred to as `TutorialApp`, is created to generate and send packets to the sink. This application is configured to begin transmission at 1 second and run until 20 seconds, producing a controlled flow of data for analysis.

For the purpose of tracking performance, the callback functions have been created. `CwndChange` logs down any movements in the congestion window while `RxDrop` registers cases of packet drops. These callbacks link the relevant events together through the simulation, resulting in automatic logging of the significant performance metrics in real-time. Concluding, the simulation is run for exactly 20 seconds in which the performance data, i.e. the dynamics of the congestion window and packet drops, are collected. At the end of the simulation, the resources are freed up in an appropriate manner by stopping and severing the simulator.

This work presents a comparative analysis of TCP congestion control mechanisms using ns-3, particularly, TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP VenO, and TCP Yeah. Internal diversity of the implementations, in terms of strict compliance with standards, is checked by looking at how each protocol behaves in different network conditions that mimic real scenarios. Additionally, it also evaluates critical performance metrics such as Congestion Window, Packet Loss vs. Congestion Window, and throughput, which exposes each variant's peculiarities and the price to be paid for each one of them. The last version of ns-3 was used, which means strict validation and reliable results. This has significantly contributed to the clear understanding of TCP optimization.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The study gave a huge amount of information about the behavior of different TCP congestion control algorithms through the analysis of three main factors: Congestion Window Behavior, Packet Loss vs. Congestion Window, and Throughput Comparison. The analysis of these elements assured the clear vision of the influence of different congestion control methods on network performance in relation to the different situations occurring in the network.

A. Congestion Window Behaviour

The gradual development of the congestion window demonstrates how each of the TCP variants reacts to congestion events. TCP CUBIC (Fig. 2) introduces overzealous window growth after the congestion recovery phase thus achieving a higher throughput in networks with a large bandwidth-delay product. TCP HighSpeed (Fig. 3) achieves rapid window growth, which, in turn, extends the benefits of its bandwidth scaling in cases of high-capacity networks.

Fig. 2: Congestion Window for TcpCubic Over Time.

Fig. 3: Congestion Window for TcpHighSpeed Over Time.

Fig. 4: Congestion Window for TcpNewReno Over Time.

Fig. 5: Congestion Window for TcpScalable Over Time.

Fig. 6: Congestion Window for TcpBic Over Time.

Fig. 7: Congestion Window for TcpVegas Over Time.

Fig. 8: Congestion Window for TcpVeno Over Time.

Fig. 9: Congestion Window for TcpYeah Over Time.

Fig. 10: Congestion Window Graph for all the TCP variants Over Time.

It is the most comprehensive view of TCP Congestion Control NewReno (Fig. 4), which achieves successful recovery from a packet loss and behaves more smoothly than its predecessors like Tahoe and Reno. TCP Scalable (Fig. 5) allows scalable changes of the congestion window and thus, it is a perfect option for networks with extremely fast long-distance connections. TCP BIC (Fig. 6) demonstrates slow-going decreases and increases in the congestion window, notably during congestion events, showing its good resilience and high stability.

TCP Vegas (Fig. 7) effectively prevents congestion by anticipating it through RTT (Round Trip Time) measurements. As a result, the network becomes more stable, and the congestion window is maintained. TCP Veneno (Fig. 8) is a method that uses both proactive congestion avoidance and reactive loss recovery to achieve stability and smoothness in the network. This is done by integrating concepts from both of the schemes, Vegas and Reno. TCP Yeah (Fig. 9) approaches this method but makes other improvements in congestion detection and throughput enhancement which are especially beneficial in the wireless networks over the one that TCP Veneno brings. While we consider different versions of TCP, namely TCP CUBIC (Fig. 2), TCP HighSpeed (Fig. 3), TCP NewReno (Fig. 4), TCP Scalable (Fig. 5), TCP BIC (Fig. 6), TCP Vegas (Fig. 7), TCP Veneno (Fig. 8), and TCP Yeah (Fig. 9), each of the protocols adopts unique approaches for congestion control thus bringing about variations both in their congestion windows (cwnd) and in their overall performance. The gradual development of the congestion window in Fig. 10 demonstrates how each of the TCP variants reacts to congestion occurrences.

B. Packet Loss vs. Congestion Window

Each shrinking of the congestion window size by packet loss directly corresponds to its response to the congestion problem shown by the algorithm. The Analysis Findings:

Packet loss is a determining factor in the congestion window size, and it is indicative of each algorithm's level of reactivity towards congestion. The study confirmed that the different TCP variants show diverse behaviors when packet loss occurs, thus affecting their congestion window size disparately. TCP BIC (Fig. 11) maintains a constant window during the case of the network congestion. However, the TCP window is drastically reduced during the packet loss phases. On the other hand, TCP CUBIC (Fig. 12) makes use of a bold recovery plan by considerably widening its window after packet loss. TCP HighSpeed (Fig. 13) shows the cases of hefty window size reductions during packet loss but the effects are normalized thanks to fast recovery.

TCP Scalable (Fig. 14) exemplifies the guided recovery with negligible drops of the congestion window. TCP Vegas (Fig. 15) decongests the transmission lines by early divergence in the window depending on round trip time (RTT) signals, and

Fig. 11: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPBic.

Fig. 12: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPCubic.

Fig. 13: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPHighSpeed.

Fig. 14: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPScalable.

Fig. 15: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPVegas.

Fig. 16: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPVeno.

Fig. 17: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPYeah.

Fig. 18: Congestion Window vs. Packet Loss Over Time for TCPNewReno.

hence, the probability of packet loss is most likely less. Moreover, TCP Veno (Fig. 16), which is a derivative of Vegas and Reno, makes the windows smaller in case of packet loss than TCP Yeah (Fig. 17) which shows non-violently window cuts that in turn limits the influence of packet loss over the throughput when using wireless networks. To conclude, TCP NewReno (Fig. 18) effectively regains after the loss of a packet, thereby alleviating the impact on the congestion window. The figures below show the connection between packet loss and congestion window size in these TCP arrangements.

C. Throughput Comparison

Fig. 19: Throughput Comparison of all TCP Variants

Throughput is a crucial performance metric that measures data transmitted over time. Figure 19 highlights throughput differences among TCP variants under various network conditions. TCP NewReno is reliable in moderately congested networks, while TCP Vegas maintains steady throughput by detecting and adjusting for congestion. TCP BIC is stable in restricted networks but struggles in high-congestion scenarios. TCP CUBIC, with its rapid window growth after packet loss, achieves the highest throughput in high-bandwidth environments. TCP HighSpeed excels in high-bandwidth networks, and TCP Scalable provides consistent throughput in high-speed, long-distance setups. TCP Veno balances throughput and packet loss for diverse conditions, and TCP Yeah, designed for wireless networks, ensures stable throughput in variable environments.

This is a thorough comparison with approximate values and features for Congestion Window (CWND), Packet Loss, Throughput and Conclusion for the distinct TCP variants as presented in Table 1, These values and behaviors are approximate, and actual performance can vary depending on the specific network environment and parameters. Each TCP variant employs a different approach to balancing congestion control and maximizing throughput based on the type of network for which it is designed.

TABLE 1: Comparison of TCP Variants

TCP Variant	Congestion Window Behavior (CWND Growth)	Packet Loss Handling	Throughput Optimization
TCP NewReno	Moderate CWND growth: exponential in slow start, linear after threshold.	Reduces CWND by 50% after packet loss, uses fast recovery.	Steady throughput but sensitive to packet loss.
TCP Vegas	CWND grows based on RTT; more conservative than NewReno.	Proactively avoids packet loss by detecting congestion early.	High throughput in low-loss environments.
TCP BIC	Rapid CWND growth with binary search-based slow increase.	Smooth reaction to packet loss; CWND reduced by 20-30%.	High throughput in high-latency, high-bandwidth networks.
TCP CUBIC	Uses cubic growth for faster window growth after congestion.	Aggressive window regrowth after packet loss (30% reduction).	Optimized for high-speed, long-distance networks.
TCP HighSpeed	Very fast CWND growth, especially for large windows.	Less aggressive reduction after loss (10-20%).	Maintains high throughput in high-latency environments.
TCP Scalable	CWND increases at a constant rate, independent of RTT.	CWND reduction is conservative (15-25%).	Good throughput but less responsive to sudden changes.
TCP Veno	Mixes RTT-based growth and NewReno loss recovery methods.	Distinguishes between random and congestion-related losses.	Balances throughput and packet loss handling well.
TCP Yeah	Combines delay-based Vegas and loss-based NewReno for adaptive CWND growth.	Proactively detects incipient congestion, reducing CWND moderately upon loss.	High throughput with early congestion avoidance.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study was marked by a relative analysis of the following TCP congestion control protocols - TCP NewReno, TCP Vegas, TCP BIC, TCP CUBIC, TCP HighSpeed, TCP Scalable, TCP Veno, and TCP Yeah - in the ns-3 simulation environment. The

analysis discovered how each protocol handles with different networks thus illuminating their strengths and weaknesses. Through the evaluation of key performance metrics such as the Congestion Window, Packet Loss vs. Congestion Window, and Throughput, the study highlighted each protocol's unique features and trade-offs. The newest version of ns-3 served a role as a tool for verification and evaluation, which definitely is a good first step to further TCP optimization. The mixture of theoretical and analytical ideas introduced practical design material and protocol selection basis. In this extensive study of different TCP mechanisms, some interesting insights were provided regarding the potential optimization of network performance which could be of assistance in research as well as real-world applications.

VII. FUTURE WORK

Future study can stem from this work by the inclusion of other TCP congestion control algorithms besides the Vern, TCP Illinois, the TCP Exponential, and the TCP Hybla, thereby expanding the spectrum of the comparative area. Also, introducing the usage of various machine learning models to forecast TCP configuration settings in specific network environments, whereby, hence, protocol selection can be automatically started based on dynamic conditions. These opportunities for future work will bring forth TCP protocols development and adaptation to networking in a modern, information-based era.

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